

the formation of three stepwise complexes between Pr(III) and SSA. In case of DNSA the precipitation was observed at pH 6.0. The calculation of \bar{n} was done using data below the pH of precipitation and the formation curve were found to be extended between 0 to 1 indicating the formation 1 : 1 Pr(III) : DNSA complex. The values obtained for log K are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES
 $\mu = 0.2M$ AT 25°

System	Constant	Method	
		A	B
H-SSA	$\log K_1^H$	11.65	11.62
	$\log K_2^H$	2.47	2.42
H-DNSA	$\log K^H$	7.08	7.07
	$\log K_1$	6.81	6.80
Pr(III)-(SSA)	$\log K_2$	5.66	5.64
	$\log K_3$	3.63	3.61
Pr(III)-(DNSA)	$\log K$	4.94	4.93
Pr(III)-(NTA)(SSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	6.24	6.28
Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(SSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{HEDTA}$	4.94	4.96
Pr(III)-(EDTA)(SSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$	4.44	4.41
Pr(III)-(NTA)(DNSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	3.46	3.50
Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(DNSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{HEDTA}$	3.34	3.40
Pr(III)-(EDTA)(DNSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$	3.18	3.13

Method A = Interpolation at half $\bar{n}(\bar{n}_A)$ values.
Method B = Interpolation at different $\bar{n}(\bar{n}_A)$ values.

Metal-ligand Stability Constants of Mixed-ligand Complexes

The values of $\log K_{MAL}^A$ were evaluated by pointwise calculations of \bar{n} and pL , where \bar{n} is the average number of secondary ligands (L) attached per molecule of primary complex Pr(III)-(A). The values obtained for $\log K_{MAL}^A$ for various systems are summarised in Table 1.

The values of ternary complex formation constants for SSA are higher than DNSA. It has been observed that in cases where A = NTA, HEDTA, $\log K_{MAL}^A$ is significantly lower than $\log K_{ML_1}$. This is in good agreement with the results reported earlier^{1,2} by us with different secondary ligands. This can be explained on the basis that in case of binary complex formation ligand (L) has to approach a positively charged Pr(III) ion and more coordination positions are available for its attachment which results in $K_{ML_1} K_{MAL}^A$. NTA acts as tetra, HEDTA as penta and EDTA as hexa dentate

ligand with Pr(III) ion, so lesser number of coordination positions are available for secondary ligand (L) in case of EDTA than with HEDTA, than with NTA system, which results in lowering of stabilities of respective ternary chelates. In case of NTA and HEDTA systems in the secondary ligand (L) has to approach the neutral species Pr(III)-(A). Whereas in case of EDTA system it has to approach a negatively charged Pr(III)-(A) species. This electrostatic effect (repulsion) also results in lowering the values of K_{MAL}^A in case of EDTA.

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Preparation and Characterisation of 12-Heteropoly Tantalatomolybdate(VI)

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EXTENSIVE X-ray studies of the aqueous solution of potassium hexatantalate¹⁻³ showed the existence of polynuclear oxoanions $[HTa_6O_{19}]^{7-}$ and $[Ta_6O_{19}]^{8-}$. Hence it is likely that the heteropolytantalate can be prepared. Dale et al⁴ have reported sodium 12-niobotantalatomanganate(IV) and have not found the works of Lapitsku and his coworkers⁵ to be reproducible in this connection. In the present communication attempts have been made to establish some suitable conditions of formation, preparation and characterisation of a new heteropoly salt of tantalum with molybdenum as the heteroatom.

Experimental

Solutions of arbitrary concentrations of the reactants may cause immediate precipitation, when they are mixed together, leading to the formation of a compound with indefinite composition. So M/20 molybdic acid and freshly prepared⁶ M/50 potassium hexatantalate solutions were found to be workable. The variation of pH changes were recorded against volume⁷ when M/20 molybdic acid solution was gradually added into 30 ml of M/50 potassium hexatantalate solution. To corroborate the observation thermometric titrimetric method⁷ was also applied. The nature of the graphs are same as reported⁷ for 6-heteropoly tantalatomolybdate. The pH at which the compound formation is expected in solution phase is around 6.2, when 30 ml of M/50 potassium hexaniobate solution is mixed with 60 ml, of M/20 molybdic acid. So for the isolation of the compound in solid state, 30 ml of potassium hexaniobate was mixed with 60 ml, solution of M/20 molybdic acid and refluxed

for 4 hrs. in a round bottom flask provided with a series of potash bulb guard tubes which absorbed CO_2 from air. Thus hydrolysis of alkali metal hexatantalate, due to the presence of atmospheric CO_2 , was easily avoided. The solution was left for 72 hrs. in vacuum when white powdery compound was separated, filtered, dried and collected. Repeated attempts were made to recover the compound in crystalline form but failed. For analysis of the compound molybdenum was estimated gravimetrically⁸ as molybdenum oxinate by 8-hydroxy quinoline method and colorimetrically⁹ by potassium thiocyanate method. Tantalum was estimated gravimetrically¹⁰ by precipitating it as tantalic acid with conc. HCl and then weighing as Ta_2O_5 at 850° . Potassium was estimated by flame photometric method and hydrogen was estimated with the help of element estimation technique (Found: Mo, 2.65; Ta, 62.07; K, 8.80; H, 1.0 per cent. calcd. for $\text{K}_8\text{H}_2[\text{MoTa}_{12}\text{O}_{33}]\cdot 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Mo, 2.74; Ta, 62.14; K, 8.95; H, 1.03 per cent.). The final representation of the formula was according to the views suggested by Lindqvist¹¹ for complex heteropoly anion $[\text{X}^{n+}\text{Ta}_{12}\text{O}_{33}]^{(16-n)-}$. According to IUPAC system the compound has been named as heteropoly tantalatomolybdate(VI).

Molecular weight determination—The cryoscopic method, as has been applied successfully by Alexander¹² and by Thilo and Kruger¹³ for molecular weight determination of certain inorganic polyacids and polyphosphates, etc., in water and molten sodium sulphate decahydrate; has also been applied here for the determination of the approximate molecular weight of the compound in the same conditions, i.e., in water and molten sodium sulphate decahydrate^{12,13}. This determination showed the molecular weight of the compound to be 3395 as compared with the calculated value 3494.14. As the nature of the compound was amorphous and repeated attempts to isolate a single crystal failed, so the true molecular weight could not be determined by X-ray diffraction technique as has been done in the previous reports⁷.

Thermal Depolymerization—The heteropoly acids and their salts can be regarded as condensation inorganic polymers¹⁴. The thermal depolymerization of the compound has been studied on the light of the investigations made by West and Audrieth¹⁵ on a few heteropoly tungstic acid. The apparatus used for this purpose was that described by Ray and Sinha¹⁶, with continuous pumping the depolymerized product, followed by successive weighing using a thermogravimetric balance and estimations at some stages. The dissociation of the compound was observed at 75° under reduced pressure when six molecules of water were eliminated. At 160° further five molecules of water were lost. The rest of the water molecules remained intact in the crystal lattice till 340° above which they were completely removed. When the temperature was raised still higher, then nearly at $720^\circ \pm 5^\circ$, the compound was broken as a whole into the basic units of lower oxides of molybdenum and tantalum.

Discussion

The X-ray studies of the structure¹¹ of isopoly unit $[\text{Ta}_6\text{O}_{19}]^{8-}$ reveals that the six tantalum atoms lie at the centres of six octahedrons while nineteen oxygen atoms lie at the apexes forming some sort of projection pattern. Now for the probable configuration of heteropoly unit $[\text{MoTa}_{12}\text{O}_{33}]^{-10}$, it may be predicted¹⁷ that two isopoly units of $[\text{Ta}_6\text{O}_{19}]^{8-}$ may condense together and arrange themselves in such a way through oxygen linkage so that there is a vacant space of octahedral size to accommodate one Mo^{+6} ion, which subsequently arrange to give rise to: $[\text{MoTa}_6\text{O}_{19}]^{(-8)+(-8)+(6)=-10}$. The basicity order has been calculated by considering the ionic charges of each unit, which comes to ten. This agrees with the analytical values on the number of potassium and hydrogen present in the prepared compound $\text{K}_8\text{H}_2[\text{MoTa}_{12}\text{O}_{33}]\cdot 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

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